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**‘I’d (still) rather be a cyborg’:
The artisanal *dispositif* and the return of the (domestic) goddess**

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Abstract

This paper identifies the rise of a series of tropes around authenticity, retreat and the celebration of the artisanal as they manifest around the growing popularity of cooking and craft as activities that have become vehicles for a larger reimagining of ideal middle-class modes of living across much of the Global North. Through media examples of cooking and craft that valorise nostalgia and ‘dropping out’, and following McRobbie’s work on the creativity *dispositif*, we argue that these cultural practices are united by an artisanal *dispositif* that fetishises the ‘traditional’ in a context of intensified mediatisation. We revisit Haraway’s iconic text – ‘A cyborg manifesto’ – to identify what is at stake in the ‘return’ of the artisanal and its ongoing tensions between the technological and the traditional. We argue that rather than retreat, to quote more recent work by Haraway we need to ‘stay with the trouble’ in all its complexity.

Introduction: the return of the (domestic) goddess

Since publication of Donna Haraway’s ‘A cyborg manifesto’ in 1985, the increasing technological overdetermination of our societies has seen prevailing views shift away from Haraway’s initial optimism to much more dystopian visions about technology in everyday life. Growing concerns about digital privacy and surveillance, the doubling down of global capitalism, and the impending climate crisis have each seen the emergence of a more complicated relationship with technology than Haraway’s early account suggests. Rather than the rise of the cyborg that Haraway predicted, we have in fact seen a return of the ‘goddess’. Over the past decade or so, the rising popularity of the artisanal – from craft and baking to fermenting and tinkering – has heralded the rediscovery of ‘traditional’ forms of making as methods for accessing forms of authenticity and connectedness otherwise unavailable in a technologically overwhelmed world. Indeed, in their construction of an identity that is ostensibly resistant to the demands of contemporary (digital) life, the (domestic) goddess and her masculine counterparts have become symbols of ‘cool’ as artisan jobs have become increasingly desirable (Ocejo, 2017) and artisan practices the focus of significant media attention.

In this paper, we examine two artisan practices that have been subject to perhaps the greatest media attention: cooking and craft. With food media almost singlehandedly propping up a number of traditional media industries over the past couple of decades (including television and book

publishing) and cooking and craft at the forefront of new media platforms and forms of engagement, food and craft media are surrounded by especially large professional and amateur media economies. Media representations of cooking and craft share a great many narratives, tropes and personas, and ongoing media interest has ensured the circulation of its discourses and practices well beyond those who may themselves be artisan producers or makers. Elsewhere, the authors have explored the more progressive and/or the more ambiguous aspects of ‘back to basics’ food and craft practices, such as the ways craft making and purchasing can be part of an ‘intentional economy’ in the language of Gibson-Graham (2006; see Luckman, 2015) or the way that alternative food practices can generate ‘more-than-market’ affects (see Phillipov, 2017). But in this paper, we wish to explore the tendency within cooking and craft narratives to present traditional forms of artisanal making as sources of escape from the alienation of contemporary, technologically driven society, and as methods for investing in more authentic connection to one’s food, home or work.

While ‘retreat’ and ‘escape’ are seemingly harmless, in the context of a global climate crisis, growing threats to liberal democratic modes of government, and alongside both of these ever-increasing economic inequalities, they can also operate to normalise a larger discourse of ‘everyone for themselves’. Within this paradigm, those with the capacity to best protect themselves and their family focus on individualised responses to socio-economic transformations, retreating from collective and more inclusive efforts to effect positive change. While, as both authors have acknowledged elsewhere, there is of course much that is good, praiseworthy and a source of solidarity within artisanal food and making cultures, it is also impossible to ignore the degree to which they tap into wider social anxieties, and it is this that we wish to focus on here.

With mediatisation now a key method through which the artisanal circulates and is made available to wider audiences, media devoted to cooking and craft are key sites through which many of the problems of contemporary life are articulated, and through which both new and old relationships between gender and technology are lived out and worked through. Cooking and craft narratives typically begin with a moment of self-realisation – a need to make a change to how one lives or works. This leads to a decision to go ‘back to basics’ and to adopt transparent making processes as a panacea to the alienation of contemporary life. Such changes are often accompanied by a ‘tree change’,¹ a decision to downshift, or the establishment of a home business, expressing one’s desire for a better work–life balance. These changes bring with them profoundly blurred boundaries between work and home: not only does the home become the site of work for artisan food or craft businesses, but narratives of ‘home’ and ‘family’ serve as creative resources for the promotion of these businesses, with individuals’ stories important tools of brand differentiation in a competitive marketplace. The key theoretical lens through which we seek to explore what is at stake in any attempt to deploy the artisanal as part of a drop-out tactic is the work of Donna Haraway. We do so for two key reasons. Firstly, her work is clearly grounded in a commitment to engaged politics in spite of life’s many challenges and contradictions. Secondly, it seems timely to revisit her writing on the ways in which understandings based on binaries positing the ‘organic’ or ‘natural’ as the counterpoint to technology as emblematic of wider social, political or economic ills tend towards over-simplifying more complex and contradictory realities. Revisiting Haraway, then, allows us to think through the artisanal’s relationship between the technological and the traditional, and the

¹ A ‘tree change’ is a phrase used to describe a move from an urban to a rural setting.

types of identities, practices and politics it produces – in particular, what it means to ‘drop out’ or fantasise about escape as a solution to contemporary social and environmental problems.

The paper begins by revisiting the initial optimism of Haraway’s views on gender and technology. We then introduce our two case studies, focusing on food and craft media, respectively, as key sites through which artisan production is offered as an escape from the disembedding forces of contemporary life. Our examples draw primarily from mainstream media available to wide audiences, but we note that similar tropes can be found in food and craft media across a variety of platforms. Taking inspiration from McRobbie’s (2016) creativity *dispositif*, we then argue that these discourses of escape and dropping out are united by an artisanal *dispositif* that offers an ostensibly resistant form of identity making and which seeks to find alternative ways of making the contemporary world more liveable. Returning to Haraway, we suggest that such fantasies of escape are not unreasonable responses to contemporary life, but they are highly privileged raced and classed phenomena that enable the comfortable retreat of a few at the expense of greater action for the many.

‘A cyborg manifesto’: feminist dreams failed to come to pass in a techno-mediated hyper-capitalist, climate crisis world

First published in 1985, Donna Haraway’s article ‘A cyborg manifesto’ reflected, and inflected, the zeitgeist of its era. By the mid-1990s, the then-nascent growth in online communications technology and its attendant hype had precipitated a renewed interest in the place of the physical body in an increasingly disembodied world. Haraway’s optimism about the liberating potential of the cyborg – an amalgam of flesh and machine – significantly shaped early feminist theorising on the implications of new technologies (Dugdale, 1990; Halberstam, 1991; Hayles, 1993; Penley and Ross, 1990; van Zoonen, 1992). For better or worse, much of the debate surrounding new technologies was decidedly utopian in outlook (Turkle, 1995; *The WELL*; *WIRED* Magazine). For those occupying a position of relative economic and social privilege across the Global North, traditional notions of space, movement and distance were being excitingly challenged by technological forms that promised to free people from many of the limitations of their outdated and inadequate bodies, and indeed, their material lives more generally. The feminist cyborg offered women the opportunity to transcend their traditional associations with ‘nature’ and the ‘natural’ and to remake their bodies and affective allegiances through new forms of human–technology assemblage. This capacity to construct new identities, unfettered by the traditional constraints of the corporeal body, offered individuals an unprecedented chance to explore and challenge oppressive identity boundaries. Looking back in hindsight, these aspirations for the future of digital communications technology remain worthily aspirational, but perhaps somewhat naïve.

Haraway’s (1991) discussion of the metaphorical power of the cyborg adopts a broad definition of machine–organism permeability that, she suggested, was now part of everyday experiences of life in Western societies:

Late twentieth-century machines have made thoroughly ambiguous the difference between natural and artificial, mind and body, self-developing and externally designed,

and many other distinctions that used to apply to organisms and machines. Our machines are disturbingly lively, and we ourselves frighteningly inert. (152)

Cyborg relationships inform and organise everyday existence and are very much the product of the military industrial complex of advanced capitalism, the irony of which lies very much at the heart of Haraway's 'ironic blasphemy'. In this context, the socialist feminist cyborg Haraway posits is aware of and does not deny its origins; rather, it recognises this ancestry as potentially both a weakness and a strength. In keeping with the utopian feeling of the moment and leaving little space for how these tools could also be used to enforce old social relations, she argues: '[c]ommunications technologies and biotechnologies are the crucial tools recrafting our bodies. These tools embody and enforce new social relations for women worldwide' (Haraway, 1991: 164).

It was in this context that Haraway rejected the 'organic wholeness' and other fundamental tropes of much environmentalist politics, specifically contemporaneous eco-feminist movements. While having many sympathies with the ideals of oppositional environmental groups as well as a sense of solidarity with its activists, ultimately Haraway dismissed ideologies that rely upon ideas of organic purity and 'wholeness'. She argues against a privileging of 'nature' and the 'natural' (as ontologically opposed to the artificial or constructed – the technological) as a basis for understanding on the grounds that it too constitutes and reifies oppressive epistemological structures. Clearly demarcating her project from the ersatz Luddism and New Age spiritualism that are currently enjoying something of a renaissance in some corners of the Western world as people seek alternatives to white, capitalist patriarchy, Haraway (1991) ends the manifesto on the note: 'though both are bound in the spiral dance, I would rather be a cyborg than a goddess' (181). 'Female as goddess', as Nicholson (1990) notes, is another of the 'prior hopes of unity and wholeness' rejected by Haraway (11).

Looking back now almost three decades later, Haraway's (1991) observation that '[i]t is not clear who makes and who is made in the relation between human and machine' (177) seems all the more poignant and politically loaded. With much popular discourse seeming to move (literally) away from technology as saviour and more towards it as the source of many of the world's, and the individual's, problems, far from being dead, the goddess (and her god) are indeed 'being revived in the worlds charged with microelectronic and biotechnological possibilities' (162). Haraway also flags a key way in which this has been enabled when she notes: 'The homework economy as a world capitalist organizational structure is made possible by (not caused by) the new technologies' (166); and this homework economy 'indicates that the factory, home, and market are integrated on a new scale and that the places of women are crucial' (166). Before returning to consider the contemporary value of the figure of the cyborg as a possible model for contemporary progressive action, we first need to explore how and why the goddess and her god have re-asserted themselves with the rise of the artisanal, in particular cooking and craft. These are key sites where both new and old relationships to gender, technology and nature are being lived out and worked through.

Escaping to the country: food and cooking

Intensified media interest in food over the past two decades has generated a growing focus on 'traditional' forms of food production. But professional food work is still primarily a masculinised

space, and so it is the god, rather than the goddess, that remains a central protagonist in food media. With ideas of escape from technology and a return to the 'natural' operating as central narrative in these texts, the food media reveal the new currency and desirability of the 'unity and wholeness' (Nicholson, 1990: 11) that Haraway's cyborg promised to disrupt.

On food and lifestyle television, it is a tree change that usually provides the vehicle for capturing contemporary tensions between the technological and the traditional. In a typical narrative – which we see in texts ranging from the *River Cottage* franchises (Channel 4 2003–2011; Lifestyle Food 2013–) to *Gourmet Farmer* (SBS 2010–) – a former city-dweller remakes his life (and it most often is a 'he') by relocating to the country, where the bucolic rural surrounds and the promise of self-sufficiency provide an antidote to the alienation of the city. These texts tap into a long history of imagining the country as a place of respite from the ravages of urban life (Bell, 2006), but in food television, the rural idyll often expresses a specific desire to connect with the sources of one's food in ways impossible in urban locales. In the opening credits of *Gourmet Farmer*, for example, Matthew Evans outlines his decision to leave his job as a Sydney food critic to pursue his 'dream ...of producing [his] own food, so [he] can know and trust what [he] eat[s].' This involves moving to country Tasmania, where he can either grow the food himself or be 'no more than one degree of separation from the person who does'. The opening of *River Cottage Australia* references the original *River Cottage* series, in which UK host Hugh Fearnley-Whittingstall abandons his hectic life in London for a more tranquil smallholding in the Dorset countryside – a move mirrored in the Australian context by new host Paul West, who moves to rural Tilba on the New South Wales South Coast to set up his own self-sufficient farm.

In each case, the show's narrative is animated by the idea of escape from the alienation of the city and the distrust associated with modern industrial food systems. But the negative aspects of modern life tend to be articulated only minimally within these narratives. Indeed, the focus is on offering utopian solutions – solutions that advance an 'alternative hedonism' (Soper, 2004: 112) suggesting that change to more authentic and transparent ways of eating is not only possible, but also pleasurable. These pleasures are articulated in several ways. The shows are typically located on almost cartoonishly nostalgic storybook farms, surrounded by rolling green hills and rural landscapes populated by dedicated rural artisans. The shows' hosts are completely unhurried as they travel to meet neighbours, food producers and home cooks who assist them on their journey of learning as they become self-sufficient in their own food production and preparation. The expertise they take back to their farms – from artisan cheese making, to livestock production, to home canning and preserving – emphasises 'traditional', transparent processes. On *River Cottage* and *Gourmet Farmer*, the hosts are equipped with kitchens that exude the culinary signifiers of a peasant agrarian existence: retro utensils, wood burning stoves, and no assistance from modern appliances. But despite the extra effort and lengthier preparation times this old-fashioned equipment demands, their cooking is inevitably unhurried, pleasurable and successful. There is always plenty of time for eating and enjoying the fruits of their labours, and to enjoy what Parkins and Craig (2011: 191) call the pleasures of 'slow living' – to 'step outside' the normal workings of time and the hustle and bustle of urban lives. If, in Haraway's terms, the cyborg offers technology as pleasure, it is a distinct absence of technology – the 'slowness' of tradition – that reveals the pleasures of the artisanal.

While each host's transition to self-sufficiency is assisted by friends and neighbours who are operators of successful artisan food businesses, food television's city-dwellers also draw upon the expertise of ordinary home cooks, many of whom are women. For example, Evans's forays into baking and the preparation of traditional ethnic foods are often facilitated by women home cooks. Jean Duruz (2004: 61) has argued that idealised images of food and 'home', as circulated in media and popular culture, are frequently anchored in nostalgic images of femininity, and in particular, to the figure of 'Cooking Woman' – a figure who offers the pleasures and comforts of being cooked *for*. Cooking Woman is perhaps the exemplar of the (domestic) goddess living in tune with the 'nature' of her feminine role, although in food television, engagement in domestic pursuits is typically reframed as a freely chosen pleasure for both men and women, rather than as a feminine obligation. This is in part because, in food television, Cooking Woman often serves as an assistant to Cooking Man, who is not 'fixed' to the home but who freely moves between home and work.

Indeed, the fact that these shows tend to disproportionately feature *male* hosts seeking a greater connection to the sources of their food through their own domestic cooking is part of what helps to frame domestic work as a pleasurable (and politically progressive) 'choice' (see X), and circumvents the criticisms that would inevitably stem from the 'postfeminist' identities of (female) 'domestic goddesses' (see Hollows 2003). (It also helps that we rarely see these men perform the less glamorous tasks of domestic labour, such as cleaning or doing the dishes!) Here the 'homework economy', which Haraway (1991) imagines will ensure a technology-driven integration of the 'factory, home, and market' in which the 'places of women are crucial' (166), is reworked to include homework without women. Men's domestic lives are frequently at the centre of food television's tree-change narratives: on both UK and Australian *River Cottage* franchises, women are altogether absent from domestic spaces; and on *Gourmet Farmer*, while Evans' wife is present from Series 2, a key driver of the narrative action is the homosocial relationships between Evans and his friends and business partners, Nick Haddow and Ross O'Meara (see X, for a closer analysis). Food television's tree changers, then, may appear as (masculine) domestic goddesses, but their mobility – their freedom to travel, to meet other food producers and cooks, to relocate to the country at all – allows them to draw upon the 'imagined nostalgia' (Appadurai, 1996: 77) and authenticity of the domestic without being confined to it.

But as well as presuming an autonomous, neoliberal subject, ready and able to exercise (his) 'free' choice about how he lives, food television also inadvertently reveals the promotional labour behind this type of life narrative – not least because, despite their focus on post-capitalist self-sufficiency, these shows form part of actual businesses, in which the shows and their hosts function as 'entertainment packages' that move between and across mediated and offline platforms (see Ashley et al., 2004: 175). If, as McRobbie (2016: 38) argues of workers in the creative industries, creativity is a 'practice of self-romanticism' that promises (but does not necessarily deliver) a '“line of flight”... [from] a lifetime of routine work', the artisanal is a similarly self-romanticising practice that, in this case, offers an escape from 'the instrumental culture of late modernity... [by] promoting less alienated, more engaged modes of [production and] consumption' (Lewis, 2008: 232). In food television's 'escape to the country', city-dwellers can find the ideal balance between work and home (where, in the case of self-sufficient food production, work *is* home).

Authenticity and connection – what David Goodman (2003: 1) refers to as the qualities of ‘embeddedness’, ‘trust’ and ‘place’ – have now become essential to the marketing of artisanal food products and the labour of their producers. The most obvious example is the meteoric rise of farmers’ markets, where the opportunity for connection and relationship-building between producer and consumer is a key part of their appeal, but it also extends to other types of artisan food work. In fact, the promotional strategies adopted by ‘off-screen’ artisanal food producers often appear not too dissimilar to those of food television hosts. That is, they often feature a particular performance of work – or, perhaps more precisely, the performance of work as *not-work*. We can see this in representations of artisan food producers across a range of sites, including food producers’ own marketing and social media materials, and in texts, such as cookbooks, that profile artisan producers and their produce.

It Tastes Better (2010), a cookbook by Australian celebrity chef and restaurateur Kylie Kwong, captures especially vividly the personas and presentational forms increasingly expected of, and cultivated by, contemporary artisanal food workers. By putting a face to the farmer and showing how their food is produced, *It Tastes Better* taps into the same discourses of connection that similarly animate food television’s tree-change narratives, the growth of farmers’ markets, and the rising popularity of alternative food practices more generally. At a time of growing concern that the mechanisation and corporatisation of agriculture have pushed food production too far from its traditional, small-scale roots, transparent making processes are offered as markers of authenticity. In *It Tastes Better* and examples like it, the making and production processes associated with artisan food are rarely described in terms of ‘work’. Instead, they are described in highly affective terms as a ‘passion’, a ‘love’, and a ‘labour of love’ (see X for a more detailed analysis).

Cheerfulness pervades producers’ profiles throughout the book: Mal and Lola Orr, who are in their seventies and cannot remember the last time they took a break from work, are described as so utterly fulfilled that their work is performed out of love, rather than a need to make an income (Kwong, 2010: 281). Producers ranging from goat farmers to ginger growers are photographed beaming with pride and happiness as they pose with their produce, their animals or their farming equipment. Rarely are they depicted doing any of the actual work of food production, and in doing so, offer a template for the promotional labour associated with artisanal food production. Like McRobbie’s (2016: 74) creative workers, artisan food workers are similarly subject to the normative imperatives of ‘passionate work’. For McRobbie, the dispositive of (creative) passionate work constructs ‘good’ work and ‘good’ workers as being always ‘on’, as always engaged, and as always attempting to minimise bad affect or displays of unhappiness. These norms governing conduct, she says, have

... profound implications for personhood, narrowing and prescribing the range of individual styles and modes of conduct that are deemed appropriate and likewise punishing those that depart from such straightjackets of the self. (74)

If, as Sara Ahmed (2010) warns, happiness has increasingly become a moral injunction that engages bodies in technologies of self-production, then artisan food producers’ cheerful performances of affective labour serve to link happiness with good, authentic food (and, by extension, with good, authentic food workers). There is no doubt that such representations are more of a reflection of

urban fantasies about rural life than they are of the realities of food production work, but in offering the fantasy of consuming such cheerful, fulfilled artisanal labour, audiences are offered vicarious access to our own (domestic) goddess feeling without even having to leave our digitally connected urban locales.

‘Doing what you love’: craft

Ideas of artisanal escape are also a key aspirational trope underpinning the rise of the contemporary craft economy and the media texts that circulate within and around it. The protagonists in the spheres of craft and designer making are diverse, though different making practices have frequently inherited gendered histories that they cannot fully avoid. But, like the leading characters within contemporary food media, the ‘doing what you love’ possibilities of realising an income from craft are frequently bound up in larger dreams of retreat, even if only briefly. Even for those not yet in a position to fully ‘escape to the country’ as a full-time craftsperson, the values and desires circulating around their practice still reflect and reify visions of flight into a pre-digital, indeed often pre-Industrial, vision of idealised work–life integration; of life as a Harawayian (domestic) ‘goddess’ not a ‘cyborg’.

Although they are less fully developed than the market for cooking-related television, in the last decade or so, a number of programs have emerged that cater to the ‘new’ post–Martha Stewart world of craft and the artisanal. Most of these have been in the United Kingdom: *The Great British Sewing Bee* (BBC 2013–), *The Great Pottery Throwdown* (BBC 2015–2017, Channel 4 2019–), both based on the same friendly competition model of reality TV pioneered by *The Great British Bake-Off*, *Made in Great Britain* (UK, BBC 2018–), *Make! Craft Britain* (UK, BBC 2019–), and *The Repair Shop* (UK, BBC 2017–). More recently, glass-blowing has received similar treatment in the US (*Blown Away*, Netflix 2019–), as has blacksmithing and blade making *Forged in Fire* (USA, History Channel 2015–) and, employing a more Ocejo-influenced (2017) definition of ‘craft’, whole-animal butchery in *The Butcher* (USA, History Channel 2019–). Most of these titles feature ‘amateur’ contestants not yet making a full-time or substantial income (or indeed any income at all) from their making or craft practice. However, this does not mean that they do not aspire to do so, nor that dreams of artisanal escape are absent from their making experience. In the British examples, it would be remiss not to acknowledge the ways in which a romanticism about Britain’s making past connects with contemporary anxieties, especially as experienced by many white Britons, as they have manifested in the debate around Brexit. Significantly too, what emerges in the United States titles in particular is a strong sense of DIY making/butchery as connected with a predominately white and almost exclusively male sense of the value of self-sufficiency. Many of the butchers are rural or suburban based; quite a few also hunt their own animals. Similarly, while the first two stages of knifemaking on *Forged in Fire* that reduce the contestant pool from four to two are hosted in a custom-built studio, the final deciding making challenge takes place in the contestant’s own, generally home- (that is garage-)based, forge.

For while many craftspeople and makers across the Global North may well seek out a rural idyll as part of their larger lifestyle (down)shift, in reality this is certainly not obligatory nor even possible for most. As exemplified by the ‘rural in the urban’ presence of the artisanal in the form of micro/craft breweries and distilleries, farmers markets, and other forms of transparent production and supply

chain processes (see Ocejo, 2017), a tree change into craft and making is just as possible in the city as it is in the country. So for many, while their ideal lifestyle may be best realised in rural halcyon settings, the newfound artisanal emphasis on craft and making is particularly notable for the way it evokes overly romantic visions of small-scale urban making that look back with pride to a time before the cyborgian digital age 'when the West made things', without acknowledging many of the horrendous personal, community and environmental impacts of industrialisation. But it is precisely this eulogising of loss, and celebration of 'rediscovery' or 'return', that means that makers can just as easily be found in gentrifying industrial urban neighbourhoods: Brooklyn, Spitalfields, Hoxton, Brunswick and Murrumbidgee, or indeed in depressed regional areas still suffering profoundly from the loss of production industries and the jobs and pride that go with it. We will see this shortly in the UK case of 'The Potteries' region around Stoke-on-Trent. But wherever it occurs, as with the food and cooking-centred narratives, there are several key tropes around value and desire that appear again and again as the accepted narratives of this process. In terms of craft and making, these are all exemplified in the British television program *The Great Pottery Throwdown*.

First broadcast on BBC2 in 2015, with a second season in 2017, *The Great Pottery Throwdown* is due to return for a third season, having been discontinued by the BBC but taken up by Channel 4. As already indicated the format is a relatively familiar one, with the weekly competition unfolding around ten potters, two judges and a host at the heritage listed Middleport Pottery, Stoke-on-Trent, which in the last decade was saved from the decay and decline of many of the Staffordshire potteries. In the first season of the *Throwdown*, the parallels between how contemporary food and cooking shows present a particular 'back to basics' escape are clear and directly evoked. The authenticity of craft as a practice with provenance is underscored in the show through reference to the fact that pottery has been with us for millennia; some techniques used by the potters in their challenges, we are reminded, are over 15,000 years old. All this is another way of drawing upon an 'imagined nostalgia' (Appadurai, 1996: 77), cherry-picking history for its romance and downplaying the negative. That pottery is central to life itself is strongly implied, reinforcing a tacit understanding shared with the audience that so much that is present in our contemporary digital world is clearly not of value and will never 'stand the test of time'. Pottery is elemental, as suggested by the Season 1 soldier contestant who spoke of his 'love of making something from scratch, from a lump of mud in the hand'. Clay, we are reminded, 'is of the earth, from its very volcanic beginnings'.

Given most of the contestants still have 'day jobs', their escape through pottery is at present partial, temporary; a time out from everyday life. Pottery making is evoked as a quiet zone, a retreat from the noise of the rest of one's life; it is a spiritual process, a deeply emotional and real activity. Again, words like 'love' and 'pride' are frequently evoked. Pottery in this context is a form of labour that means something, that is tangible in a frequently ephemeral or shallow (digital) world. Such comments are frequently offered within the show when contestants situate their potting work as a counterpoint to their main paid work. Here, as with cooking, we see a vision of an alternative hedonism, of ways of making that are not only possible but pleasurable. The essential act of needing to centre the clay on the pottery wheel before shaping it becomes a metaphor for the place of pottery in people's lives; in the words of one of the contestants, it's 'all in the touch, and the pressure ... [you] can feel when the clay is centred'. During the occasional bio pieces that are interspersed within each episode to build our relationship with the potter contestants, we get to see them in their more usual studio spaces. Most are based at home: in garages next to a semi-detached

house in a regional town, disused farm sheds on rural properties, as well as in school art rooms where contestants are teachers. We hear how one contestant doesn't care how cold their garage studio is in winter for they 'lose' themselves in their work, evoking a classic example of a Csikszentmihalyi (1991/2008) 'flow' state, where the making itself transcends all other considerations. As befitting the format of these kinds of friendly, but still competition-based, reality TV shows, a sense of personal challenge and growth through making is clearly evident and performed.

Of course, *The Great Pottery Throwdown* is just one text among many, but the trope of artisanal escape through making that you love, is prevalent across craft-related media. It is even present in the advertising one must endure to watch episodes of the series on YouTube. (When undertaking this textual analysis in Australia in 2019, this advertising took the form of bank loans for middle-class people looking to give up their city career and follow their rural dream to seek 'something more' from their lives). In the sphere of craft, the media landscape where we are more likely to see the more fully realised stories of escape such as those exemplified in *River Cottage* and *Gourmet Farmer* is online, displayed through the promotional labour demanded of craft producers on Instagram and Etsy. As we have written elsewhere (X), the mediated online spaces of craft retail are deeply performative, both aesthetically and personally. Richly imbued with both textual and visual storytelling that tends to foreground the maker and an idealised vision of the maker's world, a key part of the story being told here is of successful integration of the physical and temporal spaces of making, family and life generally, as makers 'sell the ideas behind their products and services as much as they sell the products and services themselves' (Ocejo, 2017: 19). Not infrequently, this features the maker's craft practice as part of, or enabling or enabled by, a wider tree change; the images presented foreground relationships with nature (the goddess), very definitely and deliberately eschewing those entangled with digital technology (the cyborg). Analogue tools are celebrated, especially traditional ones, but their own particular status as 'tools' and not in their own way 'technologies' affirms a dualism between the desirable analogue/artisanal and unwelcome digital. That there is money in the enabling of this dream of escape is evident in the growth not only in the mainstreaming of financial services (such as bank loans) to enable it, but in the substantial sector-specific business advice industry around it. This includes online tools, customised services and, notably in terms of the media landscape around craft, a growing body of published titles such as: *Starting an Etsy Business for Dummies* (Gatski, Shoup and Strine, 2013), *The Handmade Marketplace: How to Sell Your Crafts Locally, Globally, and Online* (Chapin, 2014), and *Etsypreneurship: Everything You Need to Know to Turn Your Handmade Hobby into a Thriving Business* (Malinak, 2013).

Meanwhile, *The Great Pottery Throwdown* represents people generally not yet financially in a position to realise their dreams of escape into full-time making. Yet, in the aspiration towards, rather than full realisation of retreat, the pervasiveness and strength of the aspirational tropes of the organicism of the artisanal are similarly reinforced. The very everyday accessibility of much craft activity – that it can be 'ducked' into in the evening or at weekends – is equally possible in urban and suburban as well as rural idyll locations. Notably, this allows the romance of the ultimate realisation of this lifestyle to remain uncompromised by the complications of its reality.

Escapist fantasies and the artisanal *dispositif*

The centrality of the figure of the (domestic) goddess to the escapist fantasies offered by cooking and craft is perhaps best exemplified by US journalist and author Emily Matchar's 2013 book *Homeward Bound: Why Women are Embracing the New Domesticity*, the cover of which features an illustration of a young woman happily knitting a pattern of a house surrounded by hearts, next to a chicken-patterned earthenware container for cooking utensils. The knitter is both bespectacled and tattooed. Matchar's 'new domesticity' neatly captures what it is we are referring to by the 'return of the goddess', albeit here she is at least acknowledged as a figure enabled by internet:

Nowhere is the new domestic chic so apparent as in the blogosphere. If you're a young woman, chances are you already know all about the 'domestic porn' blog phenomenon, which is overwhelmingly female dominated and overwhelmingly enamored of a cozy vintage aesthetic. You'll find young women in retro dresses showing off their knitting projects, pictures of steamy apple pies and overexposed shots of wildflowers in Mason jars, musings on one's love of rainy days and iced tea and vintage KitchenAids. If the bloggers have children, expect moony, angelic pictures of toddlers in hand-knitted striped sweaters and arty, backlit close-ups of infants' downy little ears. Some of these women will refer to themselves, in a cheeky but serious spirit, as 'homemakers' or 'housewives' – 'I'm a modern-day homemaker' or 'Just call me a "hipster housewife".' If 'housewife' was a dirty word in the seventies, eighties, and nineties, it's now dirty in the good sense, electric with the shivery delight of taboo-breaking. (3)

She notes how, not uncoincidentally, '[m]otherhood itself is being venerated in a way not seen since the hypernatalist 1950s' (Matchar, 2013, 3–4), and observes mainstream media interest in, and endorsement of, this 'back to the future' picture:

[I]t's not just in Hollywood that parenthood is cool again – the yummy mummy/boho goddess has become an enduring icon for the 2000s, the double-wide stroller a signifier of urban affluence. 'The old-fashioned, full-time mother at home is being celebrated – as fashion icon, as status symbol, as sex symbol,' crows the *Daily Telegraph*, while the *Huffington Post* asks, 'Is "career woman" the new "spinster"?' (4)

Importantly, and impossible to argue with, she notes that much of this is driven by increasing dissatisfaction with the contemporary, frequently casualised and precarious workplace and its demands, which become all the more stressful and impossible to manage, especially for women with caregiving responsibilities at home. Indeed, Matchar (2013) identifies six key drivers of the 'New Domesticity':

1. A rising sense of distrust toward government, corporations, and the food system;
 2. Concern for the environment;
 3. The gloomy economy;
 4. Discontent with contemporary work culture;
 5. The draw of hands-on work in a technology-driven world;
 6. An increasingly intensive standard of parenting.
- (15)

Importantly for our argument here, she highlights how this is an individualised response in the face of a loss 'of faith in communal solutions for social, economic, and environmental problems, [as a

result of which] there's been a dramatic shift toward an ethos of family-based self-reliance, an ethos that's quickly moving from the fringes and into the mainstream' (Matchar, 2013: 16). Clearly, as we approach 2020, technology is occupying a far less utopian position in the largely white, middle-class imagination of the Global North than seemed possible in 1985.

A larger mythos is at work here, within which artisanal practices and lifestyles are being positioned as the (individualised) antidote to climate crisis, capitalism run rampant, and technology seemingly overrunning our lives. 'Getting out of Dodge' and retreating into a bucolic life of one's own is the logical response to this in an age of lifestyle aspiration and Instagram. As the examples we have discussed show, this escape is frequently invested in a particular kind of promotional labour – one that suggests that the life that we see on screen or on the page is both aspirational and achievable, something that, with the 'right' choices and the right kinds of commitments, 'we' can all have, too. These discourses reflect the increasing global influence of neoliberal, consumer-oriented modes of citizenship (Miller, 2007) in which individual lifestyle 'choices' are offered as methods for investing in – and articulating – ethical, social and civic concerns (Lewis and Potter, 2011; Littler, 2008). Artisanal making offers a highly individualised response to a range of social, economic and environmental problems, with 'the self' conceived as the primary site of change. But we see in the growing media interest in artisanal making not only an emphasis on individual choices, but also individual retreat.

The structure and dispositions associated with these escapist fantasies that rekindle the figure of Haraway's goddess exhibit the characteristics of what we would call an *artisanal dispositif*. *Dispositif* is a term used by Foucault (1980: 194) to describe a method of governmentality that structures a 'thoroughly heterogeneous ensemble consisting of discourses, institutions, architectural forms, regulatory decisions, laws, administrative measures ... the system of relations that can be established between the elements'. In referring to an *artisanal dispositif*, we borrow from McRobbie's book *Be Creative* (2016), which draws on Foucault's work to show how a *creativity dispositif* has become hegemonic within the creative industries as a means of constructing specific practices and subjectivities as characteristics of 'ideal' creative workers. At a time when workplace security for creative workers is significantly diminished, 'passionate work', self-romanticism and entrepreneurialism have all become highly normative, constructed as a *dispositif* that 'comprises various instruments, guides, manuals, devices, toolkits, mentoring schemes, reports, TV programmes and other forms of entertainment' (McRobbie, 2016: 10–11, 74). Creativity as a *dispositif* thus operates as a 'self-monitoring, self-regulating mechanism' to acclimatise young people to a new regime designed to manage and intensify labour productivity while removing traditional protections (McRobbie, 2016: 38).

It is our contention that the *artisanal dispositif* serves as a similarly self-monitoring, self-regulating mechanism to give structure and a solution to the problems of work and home in contemporary digital societies. In our cases of cooking and craft, this *dispositif* is not so much about labour reform and job creation as it is about social and cultural reform and the creation of liveable lives in an age of rampant capitalism and climate crisis. In the fetishisation of organic, handmade food and DIY craft these media offer an aesthetics of escape in which artisanal making offers desirable forms of self-sufficiency and in which the home provides a source of unalienated labour – a place to resist the disembedding forces of modern life. Like the creative *dispositif*, the *artisanal dispositif* is associated with a particular set of dispositions: 'tradition', 'choice', 'retreat', 'nostalgia'. These dispositions tend

to obscure the institutional structures (including class and gender) that makes these practices im/possible, as well as the importance of media and digital technologies in making these practices available as both promotional tools for artisan businesses and access points for audiences. The *artisanal dispositif* offers a regime for dealing with the problems of contemporary digital societies at a time of unprecedented environmental and economic change, but its individualised solutions leave the existing structures intact, offering retreat rather than engagement.

Conclusion: 'staying with the trouble' – hands-on cyborgs for troubled times

Nonetheless, in this age of what Haraway in her more recent book referred to as 'The Dithering' (2016: 102), we'd still 'rather be a cyborg than a goddess'. We argue that it is essential that the (relatively) globally privileged need to 'stay with the trouble', not drop out from it. As Haraway observes,

We are all responsible to and for shaping conditions for multispecies flourishing in the face of terrible histories, and sometimes joyful histories too, but we are all not response-able in the same ways. The differences matter – in ecologies, economies, species, lives. (29)

Therefore, looking to Haraway's (2016) more recent work, we agree that what climate crisis and increasing global inequality needs is a highly contingent, preferably collective, less perfect but more engaged form of 'dig where you stand' ongoing intervention. Indeed, more than ever, the kinds of nurturing, cultivating and making skills highlighted and valued in food and craft media texts are essential for human and multispecies survival:

The political slogan I wore in the Reagan Star Wars era of the 1980s read, 'Cyborgs for Earthly Survival!' Today my slogan reads, 'Stay with the Trouble!' But in all these knots and especially now, where whenever that potent and capacious placetime is – we need a hardy, soiled kind of wisdom. Instructed by companion species of the myriad terran kingdoms in all their placetimes, we need to reseed our souls and our homeworlds in order to flourish – again, or maybe just for the first time – on a vulnerable planet that is not yet murdered. (117)

We need hands-on cyborgs in these troubled times; we need their '[a]pproaches tuned to "multispecies becoming-with" [that will] better sustain us in staying with the trouble on terra' (Haraway, 2016: 63). Repair, local food growing, decentralised and climate-sensitive production, ethical supply chains – these are essential cyborg assemblages for the current age. In this way, 'staying with the trouble' can foster collective and not just individual action. It also allows us to stay with technology. We need technology, whether it be the most basic of tools, or the digital communicative infrastructures that make the sharing of the knowledges enabling the rise of the artisanal so possible. We all remain cyborgs, whether we like it or not; there is no escape from this reality, nor of our interdependence on both the planet and one another. The artisanal *dispositif* is important to identify and name, for these are a consistent set of values and discourses going above and across multiple sites. The artisanal *dispositif* at its extreme can work to foreclose, through diversion of energies, necessary courses of action. Given the degree to which it encourages and

enables relatively privileged people to evade engaging with many of the key challenges of our time – challenges that require collective, indeed, transnational and global action – attention needs to be drawn to this aspect of the artisanal *dispositif*.

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